

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ROLE OVERLOAD AND ROLE CONFLICT WITH QUALITY OF WORK LIFE AMONG LOCAL EMPLOYEES IN JORDANIAN QUALIFIED INDUSTRIAL ZONES: DOES INTERACTIONAL JUSTICE MATTER?

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ABSTRACT

Quality of Work Life (QWL) has become one of the important topics in the last three decades. However, majority of previous studies focused on the QWL in developed countries. Few studies investigated QWL in developing countries in the manufacturing sector. The purpose of this study is investigating the QWL among workers in textile industry in the Jordanian qualified industrial zones (QIZs). Building on the literature, this study proposed that role overload, role conflict as independent variables (IVs) affect the QWL as dependent variable (DV). In addition, the study proposed that interactional justice will have a mediating role between the IVs and DV. The data was collected from 375 respondents working for 55 enterprises in 6 locations distributed in various QIZs. The findings of this study showed that role overload and role conflict has insignificant relationship with QWL of Jordanian workers in QIZs. The results also showed that role conflict have significant relationships with interactional justice. Future studies are recommended to replicate the findings of this study.

Keywords: Role overload, Role conflict, quality of work life (QWL) and interactional justice.

1) INTRODUCTION

During the last two decades, organizations around the world have increased their interests in quality of work life (QWL) aiming to develop high quality corporate culture and increase the organizational performance. This is because QWL has been proven to be the predictor of organizational commitment (Daud, 2010; Nursalam et al., 2018), job satisfaction (Jabeen, Friesen, & Ghoudi, 2018), productivity (Narehan, Hairunnisa, Norfadzillah, & Freziamella,

2014) , life satisfaction (Kara, Uysal, Sirgy, & Lee, 2013), work engagement (Kanten & Sadullah, 2012), employee performance (Imai & Watada, 2007; Shahbazi, Shokrzadeh, Bejani, Malekinia, & Ghoroneh, 2011), organizational performance (Lau, 2000), and mental health (González-Baltazar et al., 2015).

Many impediments stood in the way of the organization's efforts to improve QWL, including perceptions of fairness, job stability, job stress, equitable chance for reward and promotion, job stability, and the level of communication within the organization (Mejbel, Almsafir, Siron, & Mheidi, 2013). The concept QWL is different among the organizations, this is because each organization is characterized by a different working conditions and culture, and it is not possible to generalize the practice of managing an organization to the other.

In developed countries, the working conditions and characteristics of work differ from those in developing countries (Nursalam et al., 2018; Saif, 2016). However, in these countries, QWL research is insufficient. In Jordan, there are few studies on QWL, and there is insufficient evidence to understand the importance of QWL and its repercussions at both the organizational and individual levels. (Saif et al., 2016). More precisely, the majority of workers in Qualified Industrial Zones (QIZs) face severe working conditions, such as job insecurity, insufficient training, and working more than 10 hours each day (Azzeh, 2016). Due to working conditions environment in these qualified industrial zones, various local and international reports called for ensuring the rights of workers and improving the working condition in these QIZs (Azzeh, 2016). Consequently, in this study, the QWL among employees working in the QIZs in Jordan is investigated. The study aims to find the effect of work characteristic and condition on the QWL of these workers.

Further, the requirements of the labor market in Jordan do not match the expectations of educated individuals, which mainly include university graduates and educated people that they are not ready to accept any kind of work, which leads to voluntary unemployment. Also, there is another group who are job seekers, because they have limited opportunities to compete in the labor market due to their lack of education, they are eager to accept any job, even if it has poor working conditions.

The textile enterprises were 107 in 2006, but after the report published, the total textile enterprises decreased into 55 in 2015 (Jordan Ministry of Labor, 2015). Role overload and role conflict is another factor causing stress. Many reports on the working environment of QIZs suggest that workers are required to work at least 10 hours each day; for example, in Ramadan, they are required to work from 7 a.m. to 11 p.m. and are only given 45 minutes for breakfast (Azzah, 2016). Work overload, work conflict, low wages, long working hours, and the presence of various violations that workers face as a result of the bad workplace environment, whether they are local or immigrant workers, led to a negative feeling and a decrease in job security, as well as the existence of other violations that workers confront as a result of the poor working environment, whether they are native or foreign workers (Azzeh, 2016). With the poor working conditions, the number of local workers is decreased in QIZ as a result, the migrant workers have become the majority and they are willing to work under these working conditions (Tamkeen Center for Legal Aid and Human Rights, 2020). There

has been a drop in the number of businesses after that report was issued. Local workers' reluctance to work in these companies is one of the key challenges in the textile industries, indicating a serious problem in attaining the goal of building competent industrial zones to offer job possibilities for Jordanians (Saif, 2016). As a result, it has become necessary to conduct studies looking at the potential impact of these variables role of overload and role conflict in improving QWL for Jordanian workers who working in the textile industries in particular in the QIZs in Jordan.

2) REVIEW OF LITERATURE AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

Quality of Work Life

The concept quality of working life was coined in the late nineteenth century by the famous sociologist Elton Mayo in 1933, who conducted the first study at the Hawthorne Western Electric plant. The results were that environmental factors play an important role in influencing employee productivity, not just money. Also, the term "QWL" was used by General Motors in the late 1960s; it was the first time that employee satisfaction was measured. In September 1972, the International Conference on "Democratizing Labor" accepted the term QWL as a system in the United States. The International Council for Quality of Work Life was founded in August 1973 to improve working conditions. QWL has an impact on and interacts with a variety of aspects of work and personal life.

In the 1980s, the QWL concept became broad in terms of workplace employee satisfaction and its impact on production, as well as measuring its impact on reward systems, employee rights, the work environment, physical employee engagement, and recognition needs, QWL is a wide concept, and it is a word used to help workers to improve and develop themselves and to improve their professional capabilities, professionally reflecting the organization's collective aims and the individual's personal career ambitions. QWL has two types of goals: first, to improve the quality of working life experience of employees, while at the same time improving the overall productivity of the organization (Brooks, 2001).

Therefore, quality of working life is related not only to financial aspects, but also to work pressures, absence of hard work, lack of freedom, employment conditions, and personal conflicts (Farjad & Varnous, 2013). QWL is a complete program meant to improve employee satisfaction. It is a way of thinking about work, people, and organizations that contributes to increased job satisfaction and improved productivity, adaptability, and overall effectiveness of the business (Koonmee, Singhapakdi, Virakul, and Lee, 2010).

2.1 Role Overload and Quality of Working Life

Role overload is defined as a conflict between the times given to the employee by the organization to fulfil the demands to meet those objectives. (Bacharach, Bamberger & Conley, 1991). The difference between job demand and time required to complete the work is explained by role overload (Muchinsky, 2000). The effect of role overload and supervisor apathy was explored by Montani and Dagenais-Desmarais (2018). Lin and Ling (2018) examined into the impact of role overload, job in China, service quality is influenced by

uncertainty, psychological empowerment, and supportive organizational leadership. Role ambiguity has a detrimental impact on service quality, whereas role overload has a favorable impact, according to the research.

Previous research focused into the impact of role overload on a variety of outcomes. Purkait (2016) discovered that role overload had a negative impact on QWL. Researchers discovered, alternatively, that role overload has the potential to have a positive impact on some outcomes. Lin and Ling (2018), for example, discovered that role overload improved the level of service provided by Chinese tourism employees. Role overload has a favourable Employee citizenship behaviour in Canada has an impact on both corporate and individual citizenship behaviour. According to Montani and Dagenais-Desmarais (2018). Furthermore, the literature suggests that there is no relationship or link between role overload and QWL.

This research is being carried out in Jordanian QIZs, where personnel are required to work long hours and complete their tasks on time. Nonetheless, there are few studies in Jordan on the impact of role overload on QWL. As a consequence; this research proposes a non-directional hypothesis, claiming that there is a strong link between role overload and QWL among Jordanian QIZ personnel. As a result, this research proposes a non-directional hypothesis, claiming that there is a strong link between role overload and QWL among Jordanian QIZ personnel. As a result, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1: There is significant relationship between role overload and quality of work life.

2.2 Role Conflict and Quality of Work Life

The extent to which a person can deal with the assignments' difficulties allocated to them is characterized as the extent to which Conflicts exist between job demands, resources and people, company requirements, and regulations or guidelines in their occupations, employees must meet different and incompatible job requirements. (Offering quality services or dealing with more consumers than their competence a similar time) Role conflict arises when their job duties are incompatible with their values. According to Yeşiltaş (2014), role conflict, which is a result of organizational stress, has a negative impact on the role behaviours of people who ordinarily implement above expectations.

According to Yeşiltaş (2014), the repercussions of role conflict refer to sources of stress in organizations. Individuals may face time pressure or challenges as a result of the feeling of not being strong enough as a result of role conflict from multiple roles. As a result, role conflict and stress-related issues may impede employees from going above and beyond their job responsibilities (Jain and Cooper, 2012).

In terms of the direct influence of role conflict on QWL, the literature is split. Bolhari et al. (2012), who support the negative effect, observed that role conflict has a detrimental impact on QWL in Iran. Role conflict has a detrimental effect on job satisfaction among Greece teachers, Koustelios and colleagues (Koustelios et al.) claim that (2004). Mani et al. (2014) found that role conflict has a negative impact on QWL. Role conflicts, according to Beena (2011), have a negative impact on QWL. Role conflict, on the other hand, was found to have

a significant and beneficial effect on job satisfaction among Brazilian employees by Palomino and Frezatti (2016). Tang and Chang (2010) discovered that role conflict has a favorable impact on Taiwanese employees' creativity. Purkait is the same way (2016) It was discovered that role conflicts have a favorable impact on QWL. Based on the foregoing, this study anticipates role conflict to have a considerable impact on Jordanian workers' QWL in QIZs, without defining the direction of the effect. The goal of the study is to confirm the effect in the context of Jordanian workers and, at the very least, to resolve the discrepancy in the Jordanian environment. As a result, the study made the following recommendations:

H2: There is significant relationship between role conflict and quality of work life.

Interactional justice

When completing procedures and determining outcomes, interactional justice is concerned with how a person is treated (Fricchione, 2006). Individuals are dissatisfied due to unpleasant sentiments or a lack of impression of interactional justice and equity. Fairness and equality has always been an issue that has piqued people's interest, and it reflects the identity and the way of managing of the organization in certain elements through decision-making and methods and execution methods. The fairness that employees feel or receive from decision makers in the organization is called interactional justice (Bamikole & Adebayo, 2013).

Khuong and Quoc (2015) they examined if job satisfaction can mediate the relationship between organizational justice and ethical leadership on employee's motivation in Vietnam. The study looked at employees in a variety of industries, including footwear; textiles and leather. There are many examples of industries such as the information technology industry, electronics, chemical industry, mechanical industry and telecommunications. The primary dimensions of organizational justice namely interactional justice, procedural justice and distributive justice were used in the study. According to the findings, organizational justice has a beneficial impact on employee job satisfaction, motivation, and performance.

Role Overload, Role Conflict and Interactional Justice

Employees may assess justice when confronted with problems or perceived threats at work, according to Rath (2011). Role stressors (role overload, role ambiguity, and role conflict) were investigated as potential dangers in the workplace, Employees are being asked to evaluate fairness (procedural justice and interactional justice). inside the business..Furthermore, the study found that forms of Interactional justice and procedural justice are two types of justice. Aid employees in dealing with workplace issues such as role overload, and role conflict, potentially reducing the impact of stressors on strains. Employees reported less interactional justice when they had higher role overload and role conflict; role conflict and role overload were positively associated to interactional justice, although role ambiguity was not.

The link between organizational justice and social justice and the standard four role stressors of role conflict, role overload, and constrained scope is explained by role stress theory. Seçkin-elik and Oban (2016) conducted research to determine the impact of stress and stress

coping on organizational justice. Procedural justice, distributive justice, interactional justice, and informational justice were all part of organizational justice. Stress has a detrimental impact on overall organizational justice as well as organizational justice dimensions such as procedural, distributive, interactional, and informational justice, according to the study. As a result, workers with a high level of interactional loyalty to their organization's justice were projected to have a larger willingness to stay at work than workers with a low level of interactional justice attachment. Workers who stay with the organization, on the other hand, do so in the belief that working circumstances would improve, as well as the level of justice and equity.

As a result, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H3: There is significant relationship between role overload and interactional justice.

H4: There is significant relationship between role conflict and interactional justice.

Interactional Justice and Quality of Work Life

Organizational justice's role in improving QWL for employees of Iran's Ministry of Science, Research, and Technology was investigated by Mahmoudi, Ghorbani, and Javidkar (2014). The study included 260 ministry employees, and the findings revealed that relationship between interactional justice and indicators of quality of work life is significant and positive, as well the relationship between organizational justice and QWL is significant and positive for ministry employees. In Iran, Barzoki and Sarand (2015) looked at the link between organizational justice, organizational commitment, and employees' QWL. Organizational justice (interactional justice, procedural justice, and distributive justice) and QWL were found to have a strong association.

Both interactional justice and QWL can be enhanced by workers receiving adequate Procedure explanations and a respectful connection between employers and employees. It is possible to say that interactional justice is linked to QWL; if workers have a high QWL, they are more likely to stay their positions, which benefit both the company and the employees. Workers prefer to keep working in the organization of their own will rather than feeling obligated to continue in the organization because of the organization's backing. As a result, this study hypothesizes that interactional justice will have a direct impact on QWL.

H3: There is a significant relationship between interactional justice and quality of work life.

Interactional Justice as Mediator

Gillet, Fouquereau, Bonnaud-Antignac, Mokoukolo, and Colombat (2013) looked at the function of interactional justice in mediating the relationship between transformational leadership and nurse QWL. Interactional justice fully mediated the effect of transformational leadership on QWL, according to the findings of Cheng in (2013) discovered that the influence of administrative performance appraisal and organizational commitment is mediated by interactional fairness. According to Rai (2016), organizational justice can reduce the impact of role ambiguity and conflict among long-term health-care workers.

Many workers were hesitant to work in these locations due to a lack of equity and being forced to deal with terrible working conditions. As a result, the impact of interactional justice on both interpersonal and informational justice mitigates negative impacts on workers, according to the study, which may motivate people to stay in their jobs... This study predicted that the presence of interactional justice would mitigate the effect of role overload, role conflict, and role ambiguity on QWL, based on the findings of Rai (2016), who found that organizational justice reduced the detrimental effects of role conflict. As a result, the following hypothesis was proposed in this study:

H4: Interactional justice mediates the relationship between role overload and quality of work life in the Jordanian qualified industrial zones.

H5: Interactional justice mediates the relationship between role conflict and quality of work life in the Jordanian qualified industrial zones.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Role overload, role conflict, QWL, and interactional justice were examined and discussed in the literature review in order to respond to the study's research questions. In addition, the goal of this research is to identify the link between role conflict and role overload, and QWL as mediated by interactional justice. When it comes to Jordan's qualified industrial zones, research hypotheses were established in a conceptual model. The hypothesis was empirically tested in the current study in order to explain the links between the constructs of the created theoretical model. Structural equation modeling (SEM) approaches were used in this study. The acquired data was analyzed using two statistical tools.

3.1 Sample Size

Sample size in this study was 375 collects from six locations. To determine the total number of females and males in each location, as well as the sample sizes for the other locations, see table 1.

Table 1: Population and samples of Jordanian employees in textile industries in QIZs

No	Number of Factories	Location	Number of Workers	Sample size by Percentage	Female	Male	Total Workers Numbers
1	20	Sahab	2,540	22.47 %	64 (17.21%)	20 (5.26%)	84
2	12	AL Hassan	3,235	28.62 %	58 (15.47%)	49 (13.16%)	107
3	02	AL Karak	756	6.69 %	16 (4.19%)	9 (2.50 %)	25
4	12	AL Dulil	3,938	34.85 %	108 (28.71%)	23 (6.13%)	131
5	08	Irbid	487	4.31 %	9 (2.36%)	8 (1.95%)	17
6	01	AL Russifa	346	3.06 %	5 (1.42%)	6 (1.64%)	11
Total	55	6	11,302	100 %	260	115	375

4. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The current study investigates the effects of role overload and role conflict on workers quality work life in the workplace and can aid in understanding the negative implications of these two types of stress as well as strategies that can alleviate their damaging components. These findings give evidence for steps and actions that businesses can take to minimize or at least mitigate the effects of stress..A research model was created in this study to specify the research hypotheses targeted in Figure 1. The goal of the research model was to see if the hypothesized direct effects between the components were true..

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of the Study

Data Analysis and Result

Table 2 shows the demographic distribution of the responders. It contains the respondents' gender, age, education, marital status, pay range, and position. This survey has 334 respondents, as shown in Table 2.

Table2: Sample Profile

Variable	Label	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	116	34.7
	Female	218	65.3
Age	Below 18 years	1	0.3
	18-27 years	184	55.1
	28-37 years	120	35.9
	38-47 years	29	8.7
Education	Below high school	35	10.5
	High school	185	55.4
	Diploma	113	33.8
	bachelor degree	1	0.3
Marital Status	Single	215	64.4
	Married	84	25.1
	Widowed	18	5.4
	Divorce	17	5.1
Experience	Below 1 year	50	15.0
	1-2 years	82	24.6
	3-4 years	99	29.6
	5-6 years	33	9.9
	7-8 years	70	21.0
Salary	Below 150 JD	1	0.3
	150-169 JD	7	2.1
	170-189 JD	39	11.7
	190-209 JD	131	39.2
	Above 210 JD	156	46.7
Position	Maintenance	44	13.2
	Production	221	66.2
	Service	21	6.3
	Design	48	14.4

Standardized Loadings of the Model's Items

Table 3: Initial Standardized Factor Loadings of the Items in Overall CFA Model

Construct	Item	Initial Factor Loading	Second Item Factor Deleted Loading
Role Overload (RO)	RO1	0.879	0.879
	RO2	0.8	0.8
	RO3	0.845	0.846
	RO4	0.093	Deleted
	RO5	0.869	0.868
	RO6	0.833	0.833
	RO7	0.871	0.871
	RO8	0.877	0.877
	RO9	0.149	Deleted
	RO10	0.839	0.84
	RO11	0.825	0.825
	RO12	0.819	0.82
	RO13	-0.002	Deleted
Role Conflict (RC)	RC1	0.215	Deleted
	RC2	0.83	0.831
	RC3	0.808	0.81
	RC4	0.861	0.861
	RC5	0.87	0.87
	RC6	0.812	0.813
	RC7	0.851	0.852
	RC8	0.914	0.912
Interactional Justice (ICJ)	Interpersonal Justice (IPJ)	0.797	0.797
	Informational Justice (IFJ)	0.887	0.888
Quality of Work Life (QWL)	Adequate and Fair	0.723	0.723
	Safe and Healthy Environment	0.743	0.743
	Development of Human Growth and Security (GRS)	0.738	0.738
	Social Integration (SCI)	0.8	0.8
	Social Integration (SCI)	0.889	0.889
	Constitutionalism (CON)	0.731	0.731
	Total Life Space (TLS)	0.693	0.693
	Social Relevance (SCR)	0.79	0.79

The results of the CFA analysis show that 6 items have factor loadings that are less than the recommended cut-off value of 0.5. RO4, RO9, RO13, RC1, RA8, and JI7 are the parts that have been removed from the model. The new model with 41 items was put to the test once more. The standardised factor loadings in the revised model range from 0.693 to 0.912, which is higher than the recommended value of 0.5. As a result, the amended model with 41 components is approved for future investigation.

Reliability and Convergent Validity

Table 4: Results of Cronbach Alpha and Convergent Validity for Overall CFA Model

Construct	Item	Convergent Validity			
		Internal Reliability Cronbach Alpha	Final Factor Loading	Average Variance Extracted (AVE) ^a	Composite Reliability (CR) ^b
Role Overload (RO)	RO1	0.948	0.879 ^d *	0.723	0.948
	RO2		0.800 ^d		
	RO3		0.859		
	RO4		0.093 ^c *		
	RO5		0.869		
	RO6		0.833 ^d		
	RO7		0.855		
	RO8		0.882		
	RO9		0.149 ^c *		
	RO10		0.849		
	RO11		0.824		
	RO12		0.812		
	RO13		-0.002 ^c *		
Role conflict (RC)	RC1	0.947	0.215 ^c *	0.733	0.932
	RC2		0.831		
	RC3		0.81		
	RC4		0.861		
	RC5		0.87		
	RC6		0.813		
	RC7		0.852		
	RC8		0.912		
Interactional Justice	Interpersonal Justice (IPJ)	0.829	0.802	0.711	0.830
	Informational Justice (IFJ)		0.882		
Quality of	Adequate and	0.917	0.676	0.576	0.915

Construct	Item	Convergent Validity			
		Internal Reliability Cronbach Alpha	Final Factor Loading	Average Variance Extracted (AVE) ^a *	Composite Reliability (CR) ^b *
Work Life (QWL)	Fair Compensation (AFC)				
	Safe and Healthy Environment (SHE)		0.701		
	Development of Human Capacities (DHC)		0.745		
	Growth and Security (GRS)		0.807		
	Social Integration (SCI)		0.913		
	Constitutionalism (CON)		0.721		
	Total Life Space (TLS)		0.694		
	Social Relevance (SCR)		0.785		

Descriptive analysis

Table 5: Examining Results of Hypothesized Direct Effects of the Variables in Structural

Path	Unstandardized Estimate		Standardized Estimate	c.r.	P-value	Hypothesis Result
	Estimate	S.E.	Beta			
RO → QWL	0.022	0.044	0.033	0.511	0.609	H1) Rejected
RC → QWL	0.024	0.041	0.034	0.584	0.559	H2) Rejected
RO → ICJ	0.087	0.088	0.068	0.99	0.322	H5) Rejected
RC → ICJ	0.237	0.082	0.179**	2.876	0.004	H6) Supported
ICJ → QWL	0.1	0.035	0.188**	2.861	0.004	H9) Supported

*p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001

Table 6: Results of Examining Mediation Effects of Interactional Justice (ICJ), Using Bootstrapping

DV = Quality of Work Life (QWL) M = Interactional Justice (ICJ)	Independent Variables (IVs)	
	Role Overload (RO)	Role Conflict (RC)
Total Effect of IV on DV without M (path a)	.046 ^(sig:0.505)	.068 ^{*(sig:0.024)}
Direct Effect of IV on DV with M (path a')	.033 ^(sig:0.595)	.034 ^(sig:0.515)
Indirect Effect of IV on DV through M (path bc)	.013 ^(sig:0.237)	.034 ^{**^(sig:0.005)}
Effect of IV on M (path b)	.068 ^(sig:0.332)	.179 ^{**^(sig:0.007)}
Effect of M on DV (path c)	.188 ^{**^(sig:0.004)}	.188 ^{**^(sig:0.004)}
Mediation Path	RO→ICJ →WQL	RC→ICJ →WQL
Mediation Effect	No	Yes
Degree of Mediation	---	Full
Hypothesis Result	Rejected	Supported

Interactional Justice (ICJ) mediates the relationship between Role Overload (RO) and Quality of Work Life (QWL)

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The major purpose of this research was to look into the association between role overload and role conflict as independent variables and quality of work life as a dependent variable among Jordanian textile factory workers in QIZs. The following research questions led the study:

5.1 Relationship between the Role Overload and Quality of Working Life

According to the first hypothesis in this study indicated that role overload and QWL had a strong association. The results revealed that the prediction was incorrect. Role overload has a negligible impact on Jordanian workers' QWL in QIZs. This means that increasing or decreasing role overload has no effect on Jordanian workers' QWL in QIZs.

A possible explanation of the insignificant relationship is the fact that unemployment in Jordan is high at 18.5% in 2017 and workers with no education has no option rather than to work and earn income to survive. It is difficult to find job in Jordan and the economy in

slowing down. That despite that the role overload is high in textile in QIZs and employees have to work more than ten hours a day, this did not change the QWL of these workers because it is the only option that they have. Thus, for those who are working there and can bear with the working condition, they already know about it and are ready to bear with it. This finding disagrees with some of the previous studies. Majority of previous studies found that role overload leads to negative QWL. For example, Mani et al. (2014), Purkait (2016), and Beena (2011) the effect of role overload on QWLs were discovered to be negative. Nevertheless, previous studies also found that role overload was discovered to have a positive impact on QWL and job satisfaction. For example, Lin and Ling (2018), Montani and Dagenais-Desmara (2018) found that role overload has a positive effect on service quality as well as organizational and individual citizenship behaviour respectively. However, previous studies also agreed with the findings of this study. Bolhari, et al. (2012) did a study on Iranian high-tech businesses and agreed with the conclusions of this study, concluding that the association between role overload and QWL is insignificant. Thus, the findings of this study are supported by previous studies and this answers the first research question of this study. Role overload does not have any relationship with QWL of Jordanian workers at QIZs.

5.2 Relationship between Role Conflict and QWL

The second hypothesis indicated that there is a significant relationship between role conflict and QWL of Jordanian workers in QIZs. The findings of this study showed that this indication is misleading. Role conflict did not affect the QWL of Jordanian workers in QIZs textile industry. This finding indicates that the QWL of the workers in QIZs is not affected by the role conflicts in their job.

As mentioned earlier, the role conflict is similar to the role overload. Workers at the QIZs know that their work in QIZs will not be an easy task and they tried to stay working in despite the fact that their job has conflicting roles and they are asked to perform many tasks and report to several supervisors. This is mainly again related to the cost of living in Jordan and the need to have a job and income to sustain and survive in time of economic slowdown and the absence of a better option. Taking into account that this worker is not educated and has no other option, the work in QIZs with conflicting roles and low wage might be considered by them as a privilege in the time where their peer might be unemployed. Previous studies are in total disagreement with the findings of this study. Researchers were divided between the supporters of positive effect and negative effect of role conflict on QWL. For example, negative effect support such as Koustelios et al. (2004), and Mani et al. (2014) role conflict has a poor impact on QWL, according to the findings. On the other hand, other researchers such as Palomino and Frezatti (2016), Tang and Chang (2010), Purkait (2016) found that role conflicts affect positively the QWL. Thus, since the literature has conflicting findings, this study found that in the context of Jordanian QIZs, the role conflict has no effect on QWL. The differences between the findings of this study and previous studies could be due to the setting of previous studies. Previous studies were conducted on developed countries where role conflict could be considered as a challenge for some employees to improve their capabilities while others might consider it as a problem and an issue that affects their QWL.

Thus, the context of previous studies differ from the context of this study because it deals with blue collar workers in manufacturing sector while other studies were conducted on service, hotel, education, and large scale companies where the majority are white collar employees working in better working environment. Thus, the answer for the second research question, there is there is no relationship between role conflict and depression. and QWL in the context of QIZs in Jordan.

Role overload, Role conflict and Interactional Justice

According to the third hypothesis, there is a link between interactional fairness and role overload. The findings revealed that role overload and interactional fairness have no significant association. In other words, in the context of Jordanian QIZs, role overload has no effect on interactional justice.

5.3 Theoretical Implications

There is few research on QWL in undeveloped countries, and this study adds to the growing body of knowledge in this area. This is because earlier research' findings cannot be applied to all nations, and there was a need to investigate QWL in the context of developing countries, particularly Jordan, where there was an issue with QWL of workers in QIZs. Role overload, role conflict, and role ambiguity have all been studied in the past to see how they affect job satisfaction, creativity, organizational commitment, and organizational citizenship behaviour. Only a few research have looked into the impact of these variables on QWL.. Thus, this study contributed to the literature by examining and identifying the effect of these variables on QWL. Doing so, the study contributed to the predictors of QWL because majority of previous studies either examined the dimension of QWL or examined the effect of QWL on organizational and individual outcome. Differently, this study found the factors that predict the QWL in the context of Jordan. This study also contributed to the literature by examining QWL among worker in manufacturing sectors. Justice in general and interactional justice in particular are new variables in the context of HR and this study contributed to the literature by investigated its effect as a mediating variable. Majority of previous studies were conducted either on health care, services, or education. This study was conducted on workers with low education and less opportunity to find job compared with previous studies which was conducted on other sectors and investigated the QWL of white collar employees.

5.4 Practical Implications

The findings of this study have practical consequences for employers, practitioners and managers in various places, in that upper management can assess how job overload and role conflict as factors contribute to stress and how it affects an individual's work life quality. Overall, this research was successful in explaining a significant portion of QWL..The findings showed that role overload has insignificant relationship with the QWL and interactional justice. Decision makers and government are recommended to utilize the findings of this study to improve the quality of working life among workers and to encourage the local workers to join the QIZs so that the unemployment rate can decrease and the income of the government can increase via the income tax that paid by those who are working. Doing

so will fulfil the purpose of creating QIZs which was meant to create job and enhance the economic growth of Jordan.

6. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The findings are limited to the population of QIZ textile industry and cannot be generalized on the other industry in Jordan. The findings also cannot be generalized on other workers outside of the QIZs due to the implementation of minimum wage outside the QIZs. This study is also limited to the effect of role overload, role conflict as independent variables and interactional justice as mediating variable. Thus, the findings of this study should be interpreted in light of these variables. There is an inherited limitation in this study is the lack of previous studies that have been conducted in the manufacturing sector in developing countries which limited to some extent the ability to compare the findings of this study with the findings of previous studies.

7. CONCLUSION

This study emphasized the value of QWL for both the employers and the labourers, who may be able to utilize the findings to advocate for better working conditions and get a better understanding of the aspects that, contribute to a healthy workplace. These factors could lead to the development and deployment of QWL to satisfy the needs of workers in these or similar working environments. Furthermore, it gives evidence of the working environment of local workers as well as prospective intervention options to improve their QWL. Work should include features such as Aspects of social and economic justice, as well as fair remuneration, as well as increasing workers' quality of life.

It is undeniable that QWL is one of the most pressing workplace concerns of our time..In general, the current study's objectives were met. The findings revealed that perceived interactional justice is important. Has essential effects in the context of textile industry in QIZs and there is a need to consider justice perceptions at a low level as a main part in QWL. These findings suggested that in the workplace, QWL is a very important topic. The Jordanian textile industries QIZs. Suggestions for future research to investigate more the QWL in manufacturing sector and to replicate the findings of this study to reach to better understanding of QWL in textile industry in QIZs in Jordan. The suggestion also to study QWL among developing countries so that a comparison between the findings can enhance the understanding of the predictors of QWL.

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